

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INFORMATION AND EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT FOR SCRATCH AND ROBOTICS COURSES IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: FEATURES AND RELEVANCE

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ABSTRACT

With the introduction of new state mandatory standards, the most important component of the new education system is the information and educational environment (IEE), which is based on modern information technologies that provide free access to a variety of information resources. At the same time, the information and educational environment of the school is understood as a pedagogical system of a new level and should include a set of technological means.

At the moment, it is especially important to conduct scientific research in the field of information literacy formation, which is impossible without building its information and educational environment, the implementation of which leads to the guaranteed achievement of pedagogical goals.

Currently, we are engaged in the development and implementation of an information and educational environment for primary school students, in particular, the development of text content, developing animated videos, teaching aids for the courses "Scratch" and "Robotics".

This work is being carried out with the financial support of the grant of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan (grant AP09260464 "Development of information and educational environment in primary school courses "Scratch" and "Robotics" in Smart education").

The created information and educational environment will be used in the study of the subject "Information Literacy" in primary classes, electronic resources - during elective classes, methodological developments – when teaching a programming language at school, for the development of children. IEE creates motivation for learning at different stages of the student's personality development. It will help students to carry out an active search and work with information on their own, creates motivation for learning at different stages of personality development.

Keywords: information and educational environment, primary school, Smart education, videos, teaching aids, Scratch, robotics, component.

Introduction and main provisions

The state mandatory standard of education sets a new level of development of education. It formulates the goals of education in a new way, reveals the content of education in a new way, and gives a new goal setting for students and teachers. In modern conditions, education cannot be realized without new approaches, new learning technologies are needed. New technologies impose completely new requirements for knowledge. One of them is the ability of an elementary school teacher to organize professional activities in an information and educational environment.

In the state program for the development of education and science of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2020-2025: "An integral part of the modern education system is a developed digital infrastructure. It is necessary to develop IT infrastructure, digital educational resources, networks and platforms of mass open online courses in educational institutions, and automate public services" [1].

The state program "Digital Kazakhstan" for 2018-2022 emphasizes the importance of digitalization of schools, creation of convenient and effective tools for students, their parents, teachers, administrators of the education system and digitalization of the educational process, optimal balance of human communication and

a kind of synthesis of the real and digital world in a virtual environment.

Based on the above normative documents, it is known that the results of mastering the primary general education program, including the skills of using information and communication technologies to solve communicative and cognitive tasks, the use by students of various ways of searching for information (in reference sources, in the open educational information space of the Internet), a modern teacher should have knowledge in the organization of information and educational environment in the educational process [2].

With the introduction of new state mandatory standards, the most important component of the new education system is the information and educational environment, which is based on modern information technologies that provide free access to a variety of information resources.

The modern information and educational environment is an open pedagogical system (subsystem) aimed at the formation of a creative, intellectually and socially developed personality. It is a set of interacting components – a bank of information and educational resources, computer learning tools, modern means of communication (Internet), pedagogical technologies [3, pp. 100-107].

Thus, one of the results of the introduction of the new state mandatory standard is the creation of optimal information and methodological conditions - the information and educational environment in the school for the implementation of basic educational programs.

At the same time, the information and educational environment of the school is understood as a pedagogical system of a new level and should include a set of technological means (computers, databases, communication channels, software products, etc.), cultural and organizational forms of information interaction, competence of participants in the educational process in solving educational, cognitive and professional tasks using information and communication technologies, as well as the availability of ICT application support services.

At the moment, it is especially important to conduct scientific research in the field of information literacy formation, which is impossible without building its information and educational environment, the implementation of which leads to the guaranteed achievement of pedagogical goals. This is one of the important complex tasks in which we must take part, which is a prerequisite for determining the direction of our research.

In modern conditions, a school graduate should have knowledge in those fields of science and technology that have taken shape in the form of scientific disciplines in recent years. Therefore, one of the main directions of the development of modern society is the informatization of education, which ensures the widespread introduction into practice of psychological and pedagogical developments aimed at intensifying the learning process, implementing the ideas of developmental learning, improving the forms and methods of organizing the educational process, ensuring the transition from mechanical assimilation of factual knowledge to mastering the ability to independently acquire new knowledge [4, pp. 229-241]. Among the qualities that the school will have to form in the modern generation, it should be called: the ability to plan the structure of their actions (planning); the ability to build an information model of the object or process being studied (modeling); the ability to organize the search for information (search); the discipline of communication and the ability to structure their messages (communication); skills of timely access to a new technology and new technologies in every life situation (activity instrumentation); technical skills of fluency in the most common tools of the information society – computers.

The information and educational environment in the learning process simultaneously acts as a condition of the modern learning process, and at the same time as a means of forming a new education system [5, pp. 275-294]. From the point of view of the educational process, the modern information and educational environment is an open pedagogical system (subsystem) aimed at the formation of a creative, intellectually and socially developed personality. It is a set of interacting components – a bank of information and educational resources, computer learning tools, modern means of communication (Internet), pedagogical technologies.

Thus, one of the results of the introduction of the new state mandatory standard is the creation of optimal information and methodological conditions - the information and educational environment at school for the implementation of basic educational programs in the conditions of Smart education.

At the same time, the information and educational environment of the school is understood as a pedagogical system of a new level and should include a set of technological means (computers, databases, communication channels, software products, etc.), cultural and organizational forms of information interaction, competence of participants in the educational process in solving educational, cognitive and professional tasks using information and communication technologies, as well as the availability of ICT application support services [6, pp. 3-29].

The information and educational environment consists of many interacting components. This is a system for automating the educational process, a distance learning system, and an information and reference system. Electronic educational resources and services provided by various educational institutions act as the content basis of the educational environment.

The term "Information and Educational environment" (IEE) denotes a new meaning of integration of the educational and information environment, therefore, the implementation of this idea requires solving a number of important tasks. New forms of work involve changing and minimizing the type of personal relationships between a teacher and a student. Adjacent to this problem is the need to build mechanisms for group learning by information means. The tasks of creating high-quality electronic educational resources, as well as technologies and methods of their use are relevant [7, pp. 116-125].

For a deeper understanding of the essence of the information and educational environment, in addition to it, the terms "information environment" and "educational environment" should also be considered.

The information environment is the world of information around a person, the world of his information activity. The difference between the modern information society and the school information and educational environment, which should correspond to this society, is that they are based on the use of information and communication technologies. To achieve the educational results of a student of the XXI century, a new educational environment is needed [8].

The information and educational environment (IEE) in schools in Kazakhstan includes methodological resources and teaching materials, lesson schedules, video tutorials, assistance to the teacher, school and student, psychological support, etc. The IEE components are part of a software package that provides a full set of services and information resources that support the educational process in a separate educational institution. All of the above served as the basis of the article, the purpose of which is to study the created information and educational environment (IEE) on Scratch and Robotics courses in elementary school. Currently, we are working on the development and implementation of an information and educational environment for primary

school students, in particular, the development of text content, developing animated videos, teaching aids for the courses "Scratch" and "Robotics". This work is being carried out with the financial support of the grant of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan (grant AP09260464 "Development of information and educational environment in primary school courses "Scratch" and "Robotics" in Smart education"). IEE is used in the study of the subject "Digital Literacy" in primary classes, electronic resources – during elective classes, methodological developments – when teaching a programming language at school, for the development of children, IEE will create motivation

to learn at different stages of the student's personality development. It will help students to carry out an active search and work with information on their own, create motivation for learning at different stages of personality development. We have developed educational animation videos and game simulators for the Scratch course and robotics for elementary school students.

We present informative animation lessons that fully cover the "Scratch" and "Robotics" program, and hundreds of game tasks that will help to consolidate it. The multimedia course serves as an auxiliary teaching aid, useful to both the student and the teacher and the parent (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Multimedia Scratch Course

Scratch is a new programming environment that allows children to create their own animated interactive stories, games and models. In Scratch, you can "play" with various objects, modify their appearance, move them around the screen, and establish forms of interaction between objects. This is an object-oriented environment in which program blocks are assembled from

multicolored command bricks. In this environment, the child should not master application programs, but various ways of activity: create their own stories, invent games, develop computer models. Children in the Scratch environment will be able to independently master the basics of programming, play with images, sounds, animation (Figure 2) [9].

Figure 2 – Multimedia course on Robotics

Robotics is a field of science and technology related to the study, creation and use of a fundamentally new technical means of complex automation of production processes — robotic systems [10].

Until recently, robotics developed mainly as an extracurricular form of work. Most of the publications were devoted to the analysis of the experience of this work. Currently, there are no special studies on the use of robotics in the educational process. At the same time, due to the requirements of the mandatory standard of the Republic of Kazakhstan, there are opportunities for modernizing teaching with the use of robotic kits.

Research methodology

Based on the above justifications, the study included a survey of primary school teachers and computer science, as well as parents in the number of 151 people in order to identify the information and educational environment for primary classes. To do this, respondents were asked to answer 10 questions (in Kazakh or Russian) with 3 different answer options ("Yes", "No", "I find it difficult to answer") concerning the information and educational environment in primary schools, including determining the availability of

methodological manuals and developments for the Scratch courses and "Robotics".

Research results and discussion

Currently, digital literacy begins with primary school. The question arises: Is it possible to teach children algorithmization and programming in elementary school?

Of course, it is possible, but taking into account the following circumstances:

- to solve algorithmic problems, a subject area has been chosen that is understandable and interesting to students;
- the software of the reading programming environment has a user-friendly interface;
- to build an algorithm for solving the problem, visual means of representing data structures and control structures are used that do not require memorizing a large number of service words and syntactic rules for writing a program.

As part of these reflections, a survey of computer science teachers and parents was conducted in the Turkistan region.

The main purpose of the survey is to identify the role of the subject of computer science in the formation of the algorithmic style of thinking of younger school-children, the importance of using the information and educational environment when studying the topics of

“Scratch” and “Robotics” in the conditions of Smart education and computer science.

The survey was conducted through Google objects, the results of which are shown in (Figure 3).

Figure 3- Survey results

The results of the survey are presented in the form of a histogram in Table 1 and Figure 4. The histogram shows the percentage of respondents' answer options based on the results of 10 questions asked.

Table 1

Survey results

Сұрақтар/ Questions	Сауалнама нәтижесі/ Poll results, %
1. Scratch және робототехника бағдарламаларының элементтерін бастауыш сыныптарға енгізуге келісесіз бе? / Do you agree to introduce elements of Scratch programs and robotics in elementary grades?робототехнике в начальных классах?	иә/ yes -71,4 жоқ/ no -7,1 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -21,4
2. Информатика пәні бастауыш сынып оқушыларының алгоритмдік ойлау стилін қалыптастыруда маңызды рөл атқаратындығымен келісесіз бе? / Do you agree that the subject of Informatics plays an important role in the formation of algorithmic thinking in primary school students?	иә/ yes -46,2 жоқ/ no -7,7 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -46,2
3. Сіздің информатика кабинетіңіздің материалдық-техникалық қамтамасыз етілуі Smart-білім беру шарттарына сәйкес келе ме? / Does the material and technical support of your informatics classroom meet the conditions of Smart-education?	иә/ yes -71,4 жоқ/ no -7,1 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -21,4
4. Сіз Smart-білім беру жағдайында жұмыс істеуге дайынсыз ба? / Are you ready to work in the conditions of Smart-education?	иә/ yes -42,9 жоқ/ no -35,7 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -21,4
5. Оқушылардың алгоритмдік ойлау стилін қалыптастыруды бастауыш мектепте бастаған дұрыс па? / Is it advisable to start the formation of algorithmic thinking in elementary school students?	иә/ yes -85,7 жоқ/ no -7,1 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -7,1
6. Сіз бастауыш сыныптарда информатика сабақтарында дайын ұсыныстар мен әзірлемелерді қолданасыз ба? / Do you use ready-made recommendations and developments in computer science lessons in elementary grades?	иә/ yes -21,4 жоқ/ no -42,9 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -35,7
7. Бастауыш мектепте "Scratch" және "Робототехника" курстары бойынша әдістемелік құралдар мен әдістемелік әзірлемелер жеткілікті ме? / Are there enough teaching aids and methodological developments in the elementary school for the courses "Scratch" and "Robotics"?	иә/ yes -7,7 жоқ/ no -38,5 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -53,8
8. Бастауыш мектепте "Scratch" және "Робототехника" курстары бойынша қазақ тілінде әдістемелік құралдар мен әдістемелік әзірлемелер бар ма? / Are there teaching aids and methodological developments in the Kazakh language in the elementary school for the courses "Scratch" and "Robotics"?	иә/ yes -21,4 жоқ/ no -42,9 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -35,7
9. Бастауыш мектепте Информатика пәнінің "Scratch" және "Робототехника" тақырыптарын оқытуда қарапайым және көрнекі орындаушылар маңызды ма? / Are simple and visual performers important when teaching Computer Science topics "Scratch" and "Robotics" in elementary grades?	иә/ yes -64,3 жоқ/ no -14,3 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -21,4
10. Бастауыш сынып оқушылары үшін "Scratch" және "Робототехника" курстары бойынша ақпараттық-білім беру ортасын құру маңызды ма? / Is it important to create an information and educational environment for younger students in the courses "Scratch" and "Robotics"?	иә/ yes -78,6 жоқ/ no -7,1 жауап беруге қиналамын / find it difficult to answer -14,3

Figure 4-Histogram of the survey results

The respondents' opinions on the first question coincide. According to the survey results 1 and 2, it is clear that the majority of schools in the Republic of Kazakhstan study Scratch programming and robotics at computer science lessons in elementary grades (70-71%). The results of the 3rd and 4th questions of the questionnaire indicate the need for full logistical support of the computer science cabinet for Smart education and the readiness of teachers to work in Smart education. On questions 5 and 6, the majority of respondents indicate the need for the formation of algorithmic thinking of younger schoolchildren in computer science lessons -85%, against and find it difficult to answer -15%. The results of 7 and 8 questions of the survey reveal the insufficiency of methodological manuals and methodological developments, including courses

“Scratch” and “Robotics” in Kazakh (20%). According to the results of 9-10 questions of the questionnaire, the need to create a simple and visual and informative educational environment for younger students in the courses “Scratch” and “Robotics” was revealed (60-70%).

That is, despite the insufficiency of teaching aids and methodological developments (in Kazakh), teachers understand the importance of studying the topics of “Scratch” and “Robotics” in primary classes and the need to create an information and educational environment. So, according to the results of the survey, it can be concluded that there is, and its absence slows down the transition in the conditions of Smart education.

Therefore, now the task is to determine the pedagogical conditions for using the information and educational environment in the conditions of Smart education in primary school, depending on the purpose of the study.

Relevance and motivation for primary school students is the practical orientation of the program, the possibility of deepening and systematizing knowledge from the course of basic education. Working with a multimedia course allows primary school students to learn many important ideas in the form of an educational game and develop the skills necessary in later

life. It contributes not only to the mental development of the child, but also to the formation of such qualities as independence and teamwork, as well as the development of student research skills. In this regard, it is now especially important to conduct scientific research in the field of information literacy formation, which is impossible without building its information and educational environment, the implementation of which leads to the guaranteed achievement of pedagogical goals. This is one of the important complex tasks in which we must take part, which is a prerequisite for determining the direction of our research. The information and educational environment created by us for primary school students in the courses “Scratch” and “Robotics” is:

- tools
- cultural and organizational forms of information interaction
- monitoring the progress and results of the educational process
- access to information sources.
- planning of the educational process
- recording the progress of the educational process, placement of educational materials, as well as analysis and evaluation of such activities;
- access to the posted information for all participants of the educational process.

Thus, the created IEE for primary school students in the courses “Scratch” and “Robotics” is an open pedagogical system (subsystem) aimed at the formation of a creative, intellectually and socially developed personality, for the implementation of basic educational programs in a pandemic.

According to the created information and educational environment, a methodological complex has been developed: text content developing animation videos on the courses “Scratch” and “Robotics” for primary school students.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we would like to note that in the conditions of rapid development of ICT, society is gradually approaching a new, informational stage of its development, in which the ability to work with ICT

tools and use them in daily activities is of particular importance. The introduction of the latest ICTs in all spheres of public life and the development of the information society is one of the priorities of state policy, and the level of modern education should correspond to the existing social order.

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